

Model for contextualization: Bridging gaps in science education

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop a contextualizing model for Science education. As a basis for developing the model, profiling was done first. Difficult topics as perceived by students and their teachers were also identified including the reasons why they found them challenging. This was done to examine the dimensions that made Science concepts, skills and values acquisition problematic. Each of the baseline data was used to design the model. It focused on problems that can be readily solved and addressed like the development of a material/strategy/mechanism. To gather preliminary data, adapted and validated questionnaires and needs assessment surveys were used. Follow-up interviews and a series of concept checking activities with the students and focus group discussions with teachers were also done to gain a more profound understanding of the situation. The results of the baseline became the baseline for crafting the model proposed herein. The model designed made sure to have it crafted following the guidelines set by the K to 12 Science education framework. The results included the design of an instructional material and its implementation. Pilot testing was done in Grade 7 classes, and evaluation of the developed material for further enhancement was done by experts. Student journals and faculty FGDs revealed some positive responses with regards to the contextualized material. However, some key points for further revisions for improvement were also noted. The use of original pictures for the materials, add more activities from which to choose from depending on their interests and abilities and the inclusion of a language that can be easily understood are among the suggestions. After the identified processes, experts evaluated the feasibility of use of the model considering its overall structure. The results reveal that the QUEST model can be feasible for use to bridge gaps in Science learning among students.

Keywords: QUEST model. Science education. Contextualization. Instructional material.

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Introduction

The National Achievement Test (NAT) is a standardized test which produces information on learner's achievement. This achievement level consequently helps education experts to plan and take action with the end in mind of improving the quality of basic education (Benito, 2010). To note, all schools in the Philippines are encouraged to subject their students to take the said test to be able to meet the objectives.

Based on the result of the NAT for the last five (5) years released by the DepEd Regional Office III, a trend is observed as to the Science performance of students. Though generally, the achievement increases year after year, it had been observed that among the five subjects taken by the students, only Science subject did not post a top rank; it always lagged behind with the highest rank being third among the five subjects.

The level of readiness among Grade 10 students also marked low according to the result of the readiness test administered at the Tarlac Agricultural University-Laboratory School. That is, among the 30 items per subject in Science, not even half was answered correctly by majority of the students taking into consideration that the Science competencies were based on Grades 7-9 of the K to 12 curriculum.

It is therefore a serious cause of alarm especially for Science teachers who advocate for better Science learning among students. If only dimensions that cause difficulties among students that affect their achievement directly or indirectly will be analyzed and given meaning, it can serve as a springboard in developing a contextualizing model for Science bridging program which is envisioned to help bridge any gap in Science knowledge and skills acquisition because these two are believed to be intertwined. Skill may be impossible to develop without knowledge of concepts, in as much as knowledge is useless if it is not put into practical use.

The contextualizing model to be developed is significant, for one of the key features of the K to 12 curriculum is contextualization. Contextualization is defined as "considering concepts with everything relating to it in order to understand it better". In the context of this study, contextualization is an act of examining how a Science concept is used and made more meaningful in the immediate community of a child – that it has something to do with maximizing the student's potentials to learn while helping them achieve such through simplifying concepts enough to be understood. This feature has been based on various theories of learning but is more specifically associated with Bruner's Constructivism which holds the idea that "a child learns based on his own experiences and understanding of concepts". Meaning to say, children tend to construct their own knowledge and do not solely rely on what teachers say. It is also as good as choosing what to retain and those retained are those that are meaningful to them. This in turn, will help meet the skills and knowledge necessary to meet the demands of the 21st century along differentiated themes – learning and innovation skills, digital literacy skills and life and career skills (Battelle for Kids, n.d.).

These skills are very important in meeting the goals of Science education as explicitly included in the K to 12 Science Framework (SEI-DOST & UP NISMED, 2011) that it entails promising outcomes for students. To name some are the following: (1) it develops among learners the ability to collaborate through open communication; (2) it enhances their abilities to think critically and creatively; (3) it helps them use different modern modalities to learn; and (4) it gives them the power to be productive, flexible, socially acceptable and hone their skills as leaders of the future, among others. On a different note, there is really a need for something that is contextualized so as to make educational problems easier to address. For the bridging program, it is envisioned to help the students in the transition years from Junior to Senior High School specially so that in the present curriculum, knowledge, skills and values are supposed to be well connected and intertwined. That is, one should fully understand that without content, learners will have difficulties in making use of science process skills like observation, inferencing, predicting, analyzing and so forth, since these processes are learned in context. Similarly, one cannot apply something that is not learned well in terms of content and that which was not put into heart. In addition, the contextualizing model for Science bridging program may be a direct answer to the pressing problem of lack of task or work forces that are in line with the sciences. UNESCO reiterated that the competitiveness of a country is determined by those who intend to go or opt to enroll in science-related courses (Fensham, 2008). The fact that for a country's dream to be globally competitive through serving a million clientele around the world should be accepted and teachers should do their best to encourage learners to enroll in the STEM track and prepare them well for the challenges of the fast changing world.

With all of these justifications, this study was conducted to prepare a contextualizing model for Science education as an intervention to help students in Science during the transition stages from junior to senior high school and hopefully aid the components of the learning process achieve success in the full implementation of the K to 12 program.

Research Problems and Hypotheses

The main research aim is on designing a contextualizing model for Science Education Program to supplement the mechanisms done in the implementation of the K to 12 program. Based on the K to 12 frameworks of the Science curriculum for Junior High School, instruction should focus more on the development of the 21st century knowledge, attitudes, and skills through various strategies like inquiry-based methods, problem and project-based methods, constructivist approach, among others. Therefore, it is hypothesized that if a contextualizing model for Science be developed and adapted, students' contexts will be well understood, and difficulties will be appropriately addressed. They will also be assisted to see connections, relationships and importance of anything learned in school in their daily lives thus, helping them become better learners.

Methods

Research Design

This study used the grounded theory research for it aimed to develop a contextualizing model for Science education intended to identify the dimensions of student learning that possibly create gaps in learning and retaining concepts specifically in Science. It also intended to propose a model that can possibly help in the transition years from junior to senior high school. This study basically used the mixed method of research because it used both the quantitative and qualitative methods of research to gather pertinent data.

Sampling

The school respondent was chosen through non-scientific convenience sampling. Considerations for the selection of the said school were accessibility, security and willingness of the school to be included as participants of the study.

The student respondents were identified through purposive and convenience sampling. Purposive sampling was considered in determining student respondents for they were supposed to be planning to enroll in the STEM track to be considered as primary respondents. Their willingness to be interviewed and the availability were also considered.

The teacher respondents, on the other hand, were chosen purposively. The teacher respondents should be Science teachers of the respondent school. The school principal was also asked for pertinent data to support collected data prior to model building stage of the study.

Data Gathering Instruments

Varied data gathering instruments were utilized to collect pertinent data. It included, among others, checklists, questionnaires, needs assessment survey form, interview guides, and evaluation forms for designing and evaluating the contextualizing model.

Data Gathering Procedure

The detailed process which is presented below was followed.

Figure 1. Data gathering procedure

The first phase focused on preliminary data collection which included possible factors that create gaps in Science learning among selected Grade 10 students. The preliminary data include the perceived difficulties of the student respondents based on the K to 12 Science competencies. Series of interviews were conducted to identify dimensions of student learning or the reasons encountered why they considered such as difficulties. Journal writing was done to be able to gather additional information from the student respondents. From the teachers, specific documents pertaining to school profile were requested. Based on the preliminary data collected, a contextualizing model for Science education was designed and developed.

Data Analysis

Qualitative thematic descriptions were specifically used based on the results of field observations and interviews with the main respondents. Prior to the development of themes, however, open line coding was done.

For the identification of dimensions that create gaps, qualitative analysis making use of line by line coding and creating themes were used. Common answers of respondents from the series of interviews were used to come up with themes as basis for explanation and understanding of contexts.

In designing the contextualizing model for Science bridging program, the results of interviews, focus group discussions, surveys, memos, classroom observation notes, and journals were used as baseline information.

Citations from various references were also used to strengthen claims. Revisions, on the other hand, were made based on experts' comments and suggestions.

Results and Discussion

Prior to designing the model, profiling was done on the following: (1) school; (2) teachers; and (3) students. Notable of discussion are issues on lack of learning materials, lack of relevant trainings for teachers and overloaded work, and lack of support in terms of learning materials, academic and financial related support (for students), among others.

The following table which focused on dimensions of student learning, their indicators and proposed solutions is presented as a result of the FGD conducted with the teachers of the respondent school. followed.

Table 1. Summary of student dimensions that affect learning, their indications and proposed solutions

Dimension	Indications/ Problems Met	Suggestions
A. Personal	1. Uninterested students	Make lessons more engaging. Conduct seminar orientation at the start of the school year to fully understand the students, their interests as well as how well they are. Constant follow-up of student's progress.
	B. School	
	1. Limited books	Request for more books or make instructional materials specifically for our students to cater to their interests and address their needs.
	2. Unavailability of materials	Improvisation or request for more materials. Room for instructional materials can also be allotted so as not to waste time in making new IMs year in and year out.
	3. Lack of teachers due to shifting to SHS	Request for competent teachers for the challenges of the K to 12 curriculum be made. Involve students in learning through peer teaching anyway all learners are able and capable.
	4. Unimplemented SLAC time	Strict implementation of the learning time. Make each session output-based.
	5. No echoing of seminars	Initiate echoing of seminar to be able to share what has been learned and therefore be used in classrooms for the benefit of the students.
C. Teacher	1. Lack of time to improvise due to too many workloads	Conduct collaborative planning session at the start of the school year and devise reusable instructional materials. Make every SLAC session as productive as possible.
	2. Not all areas of science learning can be a forte of an individual	Make professional development an investment. Collaborative planning and peer mentoring can be done.
D. Public Engagement	1. Class disruptions due to extra-curricular activities and other unexpected class suspensions	Compilation of doable and project-based activities to cover for all class disruptions or compilation of answer sheets which one teacher can use in cases that there are unexpected but short time class disruptions. Assignment of support group systems which will serve as study buddies during class disruptions.
	2. Uncooperative parents	Conduct parent orientation at the start of the school year. Prepare contract of agreement between the parents and the school reiterating that learning is the responsibility not solely of the school but the community as well.
	3. Parents are not empowered	Try the use of parent-teachers log. Conduct twice a year seminar to help parents help the school in giving quality education to their children.

All the presented dimensions were used in designing and developing a proposed contextualizing model for Science bridging program that could be adapted by other learning areas in the future.

Proposed Contextualizing Model for Science Bridging Program: An Overview of the Process

Contextualization may be defined differently by different authors. It may be the use of various authentic materials, activities, strategies to readily connect with students' lives (Utech, 2008). Others define it as a strategy or mechanism that links theory to practice to make learners readily understand and assimilate what has been taught (Andriotis, 2017), or an initiative to provide engaging activities to maximize student involvement through paving way to connect contents of the curriculum to practical life applications (Bilican et al., 2015; Rathburn, 2015). In the context of education, contextualization may be in the form of contextualizing the curriculum, contextualizing plan of implementation, contextualizing examples given in classroom interaction to help students fully maximize learning as they are given easier access to learning, thus, enabling them to retain and readily apply concepts learned in their daily lives.

Understanding contexts of teachers and students were done at the onset and given the said perceptions, it is safe to say that contextualizing Science learning possibly can be doing an initiative to pave way to tweaking the perceptions towards the positive. The following are proposed mechanisms in terms of making the two contexts meet.

Figure 2. Proposed interventions to address perceived difficulties

Upon trying out the interventions mapped out, it has been found out that student and teacher perceptions somewhat changed.

The Contextualized Supplementary Materials

With lack of materials for students to read as one of the major concerns while recognizing its importance in Science learning, the design of sample materials was deemed necessary.

The developed material has the following characteristics: (1) it is parallel to the K to 12 framework's aim which is to develop among learners the needed 21st century skills; (2) it is guided by the principles proposed by the Science Framework for Philippine Basic Education (SEI-DOST & UP NISMED, 2011); and (3) it addresses the need as specified by the target clients. To show parallelism to the K to 12 Science education framework, the following skills were considered: (1) life and career; (2) digital literacy; and (3) learning and innovation.

For life and career skills, the initiative to do work was emphasized in the material since most activities were intended for group to enable each member to be accountable. In the process, leadership skills may also be developed as each one may also be given the opportunity to help a co-member excel in terms of concept understanding. Flexibility and productivity, on the other hand, would be developed as most activities offer alternatives to test one's ability to be good decision makers.

In line with digital literacy, students were encouraged to maximize the use of their available gadgets either at home or in school to help them understand concepts better. Additional digital-related mechanisms for learning were also suggested in the developed material.

And lastly, for learning and innovation skills, all sub-competencies were addressed. Collaboration and teamwork were expected to be further developed since activities are mostly in coordination with a pair or a team. In this case, as students communicate their thoughts or ideas to the group, they developed their communication skills. Some activities also posed questions of relevance to their age and abilities to develop their creativity and critical thinking.

On the other hand, in the context of abiding by the principles set by the Science Framework for Philippine Basic Education: (1) the material enabled one to see each concept as related to their being part of the society (Science is for everyone); (2) the material was designed to emphasize on the importance of learning concepts through undergoing a process of investigation, discovery or exploration (Science is both content and process); (3) the material simplified concepts through the unlocking of difficulties part and give enough number of examples to strengthen learning. The presentation of concepts was coherently presented with small chunks of learning per session building upon evidences to explain phenomena (Should emphasize depth, coherence, and evidence); (4) the material was designed specifically for identified groups with the same contexts. Examples given were made as close as possible to their own frames of reference (School Science should be relevant and useful); (5) activities were designed to be interesting and challenging aside from concepts were presented in an interesting manner (School Science should nurture interest in learning); and (6) the materials proposed several hands-on activities from which the teacher can choose from to enhance accumulation and retention as well as understanding of concepts (teachers were encouraged to use hands-on learning activities). All of which were crafted based on the identified needs of the student respondents.

The QUEST model was proposed as a guide in contextualizing the learning material which is presented below. The said model was based on a series of collaborative planning with curriculum implementers.

Figure 3. Contextualizing the science learning material

Figure 3 is presented in a cyclical manner as it can lead others to design and develop their own learning materials while keeping in mind its parallelism to the guidelines set by the K to 12 curriculum in materials design. It was designed as such since the baseline data necessitate one to start a lesson in an interesting manner thus posing a question of interest. The question of interest may be in the form of a game, an experience, a riddle, a story that tickles the mind of the learners to think of possible answers. After which, unlocking of difficulties would present to help students recall prior knowledge which they can eventually use in the investigation part of the material.

Students can extend their learning with the use of digital devices, an outdoor activity, a laboratory activity or a practical experiment.

After establishing evidences, users were asked to either confirm some theories or debunk some beliefs. By doing so, they would be able to summarize concepts using graphic and advance organizers as aid in further concept understanding and thus, would make them better prepared to transfer learning within and across disciplines. In line with this, some activities were also designed to put them in a specific situation to test their abilities to use the knowledge gained in similar situations.

All the materials prepared were evaluated by chosen experts based on the veracity of content and other salient features.

Pilot Testing the Intervention Plan

The developed material was pilot tested in six Grade 7 classes of Malacampa National High School. Grade 7 classes were chosen as respondents to see whether there were changes in student’s perception of learning Science as well as Science performance in terms of engagement and participation in class activities both individual or group. Classroom observations were done at random for the entire 3rd grading period to see how well lessons were implemented with the use of the proposed material and strategies for teaching. Journal writing was requested from the students to determine possible changes or progress in various aspects.

Based on classroom observations the following are noted:

Table 2. Consolidated classroom observation results

Aspect observed	Observer 1	Observer 2
The setting	The classrooms were space-wise for the number of students. Temperature and lighting are moderately acceptable. Some classrooms have a significant number of postings which were believed to have an impact in student’s ability and interest to learn.	The classrooms seemed to be okay with the number of students that the school had per session. There was enough space for interaction or activities that the teacher facilitates. However, there were times when the classroom was not well-arranged which sometimes made the teacher unable to deliver his lesson on time.
The teacher	Generally, the teacher seemed to be very approachable but some students took advantage of that good characteristic.	The teacher seemed to be very considerate and sensitive to the needs of the students. He always tried his best to answer student questions.
The students	The student’s behavior varies depending on schedule. Some seem sleepy especially during very early morning sessions. Some seem to be restless during times when dismissal time is near. There are some classes where majority of the students seem to be very willing to learn. They participated in the activities and effort was seen in their submitted outputs. They seemed to enjoy group activities very much though there were times that group works became disadvantageous for a few who really were not participating very well.	The students were unique from each other. There were some who seemed to be very willing and interested in listening to discussions, participated in the activities and shared their insights. There were also some who seemed to go to school just for the sake of going to school. Nonetheless, I saw their effort (no matter how small) to still fit in and get a passing mark. But this was very notable, majority of them seemed to be very interested in seeing things concretely or if they were asked to explore on something; if they saw what they are discussing or if they did activities which include games/play. They were also very excited whenever they go out of their classroom during their Science class.
The lesson proper	The lessons implemented were in Physics for Grade 7. The lesson objectives were age appropriate, and content was parallel with the competencies set by DepEd’s K to 12 curriculum.	The content of the lesson was a bit challenging for students who were not mathematically inclined but since ample amount of examples were given, lessons were seemingly easy to be understood.

Aspect observed	Observer 1	Observer 2
The lesson implementation	The lessons were implemented very well though some disruptions happen at times due to different reasons (sometimes because of student misbehavior or their being uninterested to listen). However, it was observed that they were very active when activities are given and they grouped together to accomplish tasks. They were also very willing to listen if graphics were shown. They love to discuss their findings with their classmates though sometimes some hesitations were sensed when they were called to present their outputs in the class.	In terms of lesson implementation, sometimes it was smooth, sometimes it became challenging. Challenging lesson implementation usually happened in lessons with computations. Maybe, majority of the students were really not so inclined with Mathematics but I observed that specific techniques were employed by the teacher which made the students remember things easier. One excellent thing noted was the use of "magic triangle" to make the connection of concepts easier to be remembered. In terms of how students responded to the activities, I saw that they were very willing to participate if a support system was assigned to help them. They also became more willing to help their classmates in return which eliminated competition but rather encouraged collaboration.
Other notable observations	The teacher did his best all the time to implement the lesson as planned using the materials in the kit which was part of the module given.	Students participated very well given the proper resources and teacher support. Classmates were also very good support system for enhancing learning. Though during tests, results were not too high, when asked about practical issues using the language that they speak, they were able to answer even the application questions which led me to hypothesize that language used was also very important.

The classroom observation notes were consolidated and summarized to get a clear view of the pilot testing activity both for the material and the lesson implementation. Some limitations were noted and presented during FGDs which were considered as notable reflections as bases for improvement plans to be implemented for the next school year.

Based on the consolidated data gathered, it is noteworthy that students really are more interested and motivated to learn when they are given different activities, when they are presented concepts with materials that are captivating, when they are encouraged to work with others and share their thoughts in their most comfortable language of expression. These are all verifications of previous studies conducted by Baker et al., (2009) on student engagement and attention, Klasser's (2006) concept on meaningfulness brought about by emotional response, familiarity and activity and social interaction, Kalchik and Oertle's (2010) active classroom activities and Crawford's (2001) cooperative learning.

Meeting with curriculum implementers ("Drop or Adopt", "Craft or Crop")

After intervention planning and pilot testing of the intervention plans, meetings were set up with curriculum planners to try to examine and evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the activities done. For the module content and activities, there were some things that were considered to be adapted. Teachers said that it would be better to adapt the materials then had it improved every year so that they would not do an entirely new one ever year. This would save time, resources, and energy. They planned to have the materials in one area of the school for future reference. They also suggested that they collected PowerPoint presentations which they could couple with the modules prepared in anticipation of problems that might be encountered regarding the reproduction of modules especially so that any form of collection of school fees was now prohibited by the Department of Education.

For the implementation of lesson, it was suggested that the model be made more dynamic.

Figure 4. Contextualizing science learning implementation

Some justifications for the modifications done were: (1) when the lessons were implemented it was observed that even the questions raised were engaging, it can also unlock difficulties or help students recall their experiences; (2) there were also times that when students did activities they were already extending their learning or transmitted learning in different contexts; (3) summarizing concepts could also help students unlock more difficulties to be more prepared to transmit learning, etc. Therefore the model becomes more encompassing; it covers both the module as a material for learning and its classroom implementation.

Sample Materials' Evaluation

Upon completion of the sample materials, experts in K to 12 Science content and lesson implementation evaluated the material. The experts were chosen on the basis of: (1) were Science teachers or practitioners for at least five (5) years; (2) had attended seminars and trainings with regards to Science teaching implementation at least in the Regional Level; and (3) had experienced writing similar learning materials.

The experts evaluated the material in terms of the following components: objectives, content, organization, usability, evaluation, language used, and illustrations. The following table summarizes the material evaluator's ratings with their corresponding comments and suggestions.

Table 3. Material evaluator's ratings, comments and suggestions

Indicator	Rating	Verbal Description	Comments/ Suggestions
Objectives	4.94	Excellent	Objectives were copied from the recommended objectives of K to 12.
Content	4.16	Very good	More in-depth treatment of concept recommended. Make activities short so as not to consume more time than for the lesson proper.
Organization (procedures/ methods/ presentation)	4.29	Excellent	The use of equation editor, latex or any other app for writing equations is suggested. The layout of the module may be improved such as the sectioning of topics, space for student answers, ease of locating key answers, "boxing" or highlighting important concepts, "try this out" activities, etc. Be consistent on the explicit use of title in all the modules like "Activity", "Summary", etc. The list of references seems too small to be read.
Usability	4.14	Very good	---
Evaluation	4.51	Excellent	Do not provide the answer key to the students. Don't let them check their own answers.
Language Used	4.90	Excellent	A language expert may be requested to check the wording, grammar, etc. of the module. Do not use the first person.
Illustrations	4.49	Excellent	Since most of the photos are all caricatures, it is suggested to use original drawings.
Overall	4.49	Excellent	Generally, the module is appropriate for use in Grade 7.

Comments and suggestions were noted as part of the revisions made to improve the material. The material upon revision therefore was chunked into smaller ideas specifying time frame of completion of all activities presented. It retained, however, the use of communicative language as it is one of the key features of a module (Bulusan, 2018). The material is as if talking with the users since it is a great strategy to help students own their learning and thus, develop accountability and responsibility as learners. Answers key page was separated as well as the alternative activities. It was only upon the teacher's decision which to use according to student's abilities and capacities to learn without compromising the achievement of aims and competencies set in the curriculum guides.

The Contextualizing Model for Science Bridging Program

The proposed contextualizing model which is presented and discussed in detail was designed based on the preliminary data collected through various ways.

Figure 5. The tried out contextualizing model for Science Bridging Program

The model was envisioned to be holistic in its approach to address gaps from earlier stages of Junior High School level. This was done to avoid accumulating gaps that would be detrimental to student's transition from Junior to Senior High School level.

The first phase focused on identifying the available resources in the school, in the community and in the student's home to see what things may be used to simplify and maximize learning. The baseline was established to be able to fully understand the whole phenomenon that caused one thing to happen which in this study was termed as context. Each of the phenomena was established and analyzed for further understanding and was used as basis for developing interventions needed to contextualize Science learning fully. Aside from examining the available and functional facilities, equipment and materials that aided learning, the phenomenon on what caused difficulties were also identified and analyzed so that solutions would be mapped and tried out.

After analyzing the baseline data, each was considered to design materials, strategies and mechanisms to address the gaps. The plan was contextualized in such a way that local problems were addressed with local solutions. The solutions to solve Science learning difficulties were addressed based on the needs of the students, their interests, capabilities, and abilities. Example mechanisms were the development of contextualized material that was parallel to the advocacy of the Science K to 12 framework, to develop scientifically literate individuals who have the basic 21st century skills. The developed material had the following characteristics: (1) inquiry-based; (2) encouraged learning through varied modalities; (3) developed collaborative and communication-able individuals; (4) developed innovative individuals in terms of how they transfer knowledge in different contexts; and (5) prepared students to be naturally curious individuals who are willing to learn more from their learning experiences. Classroom strategies for lesson implementation also followed the cycle only that it is more dynamic.

After designing materials and strategies or mechanisms, reflections were done to reassess the effectiveness of the intervention plan. Journal writing was requested from the students and collaborative discussion with curriculum implementers were done so as to have a better understanding of things. Implementers made this as a basis of “dropping or adopting” the mechanism.

Dropping in the context of the study was to disregard the planned intervention due to its ineffectiveness in terms of delivery of instruction and student learning. Adopting a mechanism should be an offshoot of the material/strategy/mechanism being found effective upon implementation.

After analyzing the feedback of the learners as well as the co-planners, the curriculum implementers would be prompted to make decisions as to either they would “crop” whatever is existing or “craft” a new one to lean in more to student’s needs and abilities. In the light of the study, one will “crop” an existing material/strategy/mechanism as it was deemed necessary. This would allow implementers to identify the strengths and improve whatever was seen as not appropriate or effective in contextualizing. “Craft”-ing, on the other hand, will be done when one mechanism was totally not effective and it was better to drop it and craft a totally new one.

Specific for the area of study, the framework that follows shows the contextualizing model used for bridging Science competencies as students move up to Senior High School. The said contextualizing model was based on the baseline or preliminary data gathered through questionnaires and series of interviews and concept checking activities done. It is presented in an acronym type to specify the steps needed to contextualize.

The components (specific things done per phase) of the QUEST model proposed as a contextualizing model for Science Bridging program is specified below.

Figure 6. Short description of the QUEST Model

Feasibility of Use of the Proposed Contextualizing Model for Science Bridging Program

The model proposed herein as a result of the established data gathered from both student and teacher respondents was subjected for evaluation of its feasibility to be used as a contextualizing model for Science Bridging program. The instrument used was first validated by chosen experts to include school heads, curriculum implementers and practitioners, and curriculum, assessment and evaluation experts. The validated instrument made use of a modified 4-point Likert scale to identify the respondent's degree of agreement or disagreement along 5 specific themes. The themes used were: (1) structure of the contextualizing model which focused on the general layout of the model including language used, transition, symbols, etc.; (2) perceived context which focused on the functionality of the model, consensus of the settings, goals and objectives; (3) input which gives emphasis on the availability of resources including personal and accessible materials and other particulars like costs, results, advantages, disadvantages and other factors; (4) perceived process which centers on the interaction among evaluators, decision makers, stakeholders and others in implementing and refining the design and working procedures; and lastly (5) the perceived product which is on the judgments about the objectives, materials and worth of the program including the impact, effectiveness, sustainability and transportability (Brinck et al., 2002; Jansen & Reddy, 1994; Jeng, 2005; Joo et al., 2011; Oulanov & Pajarillo, 2002; Nielsen, 2020; Nielsen & Mack, 1994; Sinkkonen et al., 2009; Tokmak et al., 2013).

Table 4 specifies the evaluation of the chosen experts and practitioners as to the feasibility of use of the proposed contextualizing model for Science bridging program. The comments and suggestions of the evaluators were specified above which can be used as a springboard for consideration of future improvements. As for the structure of the model, it is notable that it is easy to learn, to remember, to be efficient, pleasing and adaptable among others (Jansen & Reddy, 1994; Joo et al., 2011; Oulanov & Pajarillo, 2002). Among the evaluators' comments were the following: (1) revise the aesthetic part of the model; (2) Contextualizing is not indicative of a model but rather on the content of the IMs for a certain curriculum; and (3) find a way to indicate their r^2 value because this will give additional strength/credit why the arrows are pointed to the other parameters.

The aesthetic part of the model pertains to whether the model is subjectively pleasing or not. Arrows were chosen very well which is adaptable to the process undergone during the pilot testing which has been a consequent result of data gathering. It includes series of informal semi-structured interviews from both the student and teacher respondents and the focus group discussions conducted. To make it more functional, it had been further suggested that if extensions be made, extensions would be shown in every phase and not just in the "extend" or the intervention part so as to guide users especially the curriculum implementers or whoever would be using the model. Contextualization, on the other hand, was only seen on the IM content and implementation part of the model which was not exactly the case since even at the onset, the research tried to contextualize even the key players of the teaching and learning process by examining and analyzing the general context (Estrada & Dubois, 2010) which was further confirmed when themes were created based on the dimensions that create gaps among Science learners.

Table 4. Evaluation of the model's feasibility of use

Indicator	Rating	Verbal Description	Comments/ Suggestions
Structure	3.71	Very feasible	Revise the aesthetic part of the model. Contextualizing is not indicative of a model but rather on the content of the IMs for a particular curriculum. If it is possible, find a way to indicate their r^2 value because this will give additional strength/credit why the arrows are pointed to the other parameters.
Context	3.74	Very feasible	Be more specific on what difficulties were addressed using the model.
Input	3.60	Very feasible	The budget-related function is not included in the model.
Process	3.71	Very feasible	Mostly are indicative of the E part only.
Product	3.69	Very feasible	Some indicators cannot be adequately measured unless tried out (i.e., impact and worthiness of continuous implementation).
Overall Mean	3.69	Very feasible	May be given a chance to be tried out to address other dimensions of student learning as discussed (ie parent involvement).

Also, even until the last phase where collaborative planning was suggested that the contexts of teachers who would be implementing the plans were taken into consideration. This holds true that curriculum implementers are "more than just implementers" (Espedillon, 2018). That, DepEd can prescribe but it is still up to the implementer "how" he/she will implement the lesson depending on the type of resources available as well as the abilities and capacities of the learners and as long as competencies will still be met. Lastly, to strengthen claims of why arrows were headed from each phase to another, the correlation matrix value and its significance should have been shown. This was a direct and actual limitation of the study since the main data gathered were mostly qualitative.

In terms of perceived context, it was suggested that difficulties to be addressed should be specified because they served as a basis of the success of implementation (McCurrie, 2009). Though success would depend on the persons involved, still it should be specified as a basis for evaluating how well implementations were. In the context of this study, success would depend on whether the gaps identified were truly closed or at least narrowed down. Based on the student journals, perceptions were changed like they thought it was a great leap as it helped them carry through the challenges of Science learning.

The budget-related functions of the proposed model were silent. As suggested, it could have been better if it was made more explicit. In this case, it confirmed findings of various studies as to the importance of building partnerships for funding purposes (Estrada & Dubois, 2010). However, this was another limitation of the study since partnerships were not yet established as probable funding agencies. This might be one of the unique features of the model as a bridging program as it is not intentionally be made out of the school year but rather as part of the actual curriculum. It would be made possible because of joint efforts of students and teachers to involve other stakeholders in the future. Therefore, there is not much needed extra financial burdens as bridging programs are perceived to be (ASCD, 2004; Roderick et al., 2003).

With regards to the process, it was noted that only the Extend part of the model where contextualizing is explicit. However, the research process would disagree because at the first and last two parts of the model, the contexts of the key players and their environment which may have directly affect implementation were considered. Prior to designing interventions, teacher, student and community contexts were examined and were the bases for the development of materials and strategies for implementation. After which, the contexts of the implementers were again considered as they decided on whether to “drop or adopt” and/or “crop or craft” the proposed materials, strategies and mechanisms based on their abilities and perceived competencies. This was done to contextualize and to bridge the identified gaps. In this light, Quinn (2016) accentuates the importance of understanding contexts. It helps one to situate learning properly and enable one to transfer learning in a more flexible manner thus maximizing learning. It also has the ability to make one more adaptable as relevance is seen in the correct context.

Along the perceived product of the model, there were identified indicators which according to experts cannot be fully measured. These were the worthiness to be continuously implemented as well as the model’s effectiveness in bridging gaps in learning. This was a good observation as it cannot really fully measure such given that the study only tried out the model for just one school year in one school and in six Grade 7 classes only. McCurrie (2009) stated that a program’s measure of success defines its worthiness for continuous implementation. May it be in the perspective of different key players, it is very important to take note of success indicators as any of the following (1) when primary goals are achieved; (2) when knowledge and skills are improved; and (3) when learners are able to use their own language and feel satisfied not only along their abilities which is more closely associated with academic terms but rather in general life satisfaction because they do things according to their interests. In the light of the present study though, a success indicator of the model would depend on whether the gaps are bridged specifically in Science learning which as of this moment is not yet fully established.

Improved Contextualizing Model for Science Bridging Program

Due to the suggestions given by experts and the need for improvement to further fit the needs of the clients and close gaps identified in the study, modifications were made including the short descriptions for each of the phase of the model.

Presentation to curriculum implementers was done to guide them on the use of the proposed contextualizing model for Science bridging program. Explanations as to the model’s relevance were also made clear to them to avoid confusion in the hope of attaining good results as envisioned after its full implementation.

Figure 7. Proposed contextualizing model for Science Bridging Program

A. QUEST model as a Contextualizing Model

The proposed QUEST model was considered contextualizing because of the following features: (1) it was based on real contexts of the key players of the learning process; (2) it contextualized learning as it examined what was best for the students; (3) it contextualized the intervention plans and actual implementation as it involved the curriculum implementers.

Real context as it was used in the study pertains to one’s understanding where the key players – students and teachers – come from. Their perceptions, abilities, interests were focused.

The baseline data were used to design interventions to fit their expectations and consequently changed pre-conceived notions. From the developed model, it was proven that perceptions mattered as much as interests with the majority of students saying indirectly that they were being shaped by their perceptions. Perceptions such as those related to their past experiences or that of other students.

Stating what was best for the students was based on the results of interviews. Majority of the respondents claimed that they learned best with anything that was simplified or anything that they saw or did, they became more interested with practice sets, games and video clips as part of the lesson or having worked together with a peer or with a group. They also communicated their thoughts better with the use of either their local dialect or the national language. Therefore, the material designed and implementation mechanism done considered the key features as stated by the students. It was tailored fit for the student's needs so as to increase engagement and consequently increased achievement with regards to Science knowledge and skills acquisition.

With regards to the curriculum implementers' involvement in the process, it is safe to say that they were involved from needs assessment (Q), planning (U), intervention (E), evaluation (S) and decision making (T) which were all key components of the proposed model.

B. QUEST model as a Science Bridging program

Unlike the usual bridge programs which focuses on bridging high school competencies and prepare students for college and/or from university to career path (Barnett et al., 2012; Estrada & Dubois, 2010; Fellhoelter, 2011; Lakeside School, n.d.; Roderick et al., 2003), the Science bridging program proposed herein primarily bridges identified gaps in Science learning and aims to close or at least narrow down the gap so as not to pile up difficulties in the succeeding years. Competencies may be different but as it was proven by studies, accumulated difficulties if not appropriately addressed will detrimentally affect the acquisitions of new and more advanced knowledge and skills (Filipatali, 2013; Bransford et al., 2000) which are both needed in academic experience and career preparation.

In this study, the bridging program considered contexts of teachers and students, thus it was designed with focus on intervention plans of improving pre-conceived notions in Physics concepts learning which was believed to eventually improve their performance in the said area of study. The bridging program was also designed not only for individual learners but for all students as they are given opportunities to effect change to each other.

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